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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****THE CONTENT OF DNA IN CELLS OF ENDOMETRY WHEN
USING SILVER-CONTAINING INTRAUTERINE DEVICES.**¹Petrov Yu.A., ²Kupina A.D.

FGBOU VO «Rostov State Medical University» of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, 344022, Rostov-on-Don, Russia.

¹ Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology № 2, Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Rostov State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Rostov-on-Don, Russian Federation - mr.doktorpetrov@mail.ru²Clinical Resident of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology №2 Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Rostov State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, 344022, Rostov-on-Don, Russian Federation – anastasya1997@bk.ru**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

Aim. The purpose of this study was to identify the proliferative properties of the endometrium, and therefore, to assess the risk of possible malignancy when using silver-containing IUDs by research of the DNA content in the epithelial cells of the glands of the uterine mucosa in women using this method of contraception.

Materials and methods. The DNA content in the epithelial cells of the uterine mucosa glands was studied in 86 women of childbearing age with a normal menstrual cycle, having a history of one or more pregnancies and using silver-containing IUDs from 6 months to 7 years. Endometrial biopsy with the microcurette or obtaining endometrial scrapings were performed on the 8-10th or 19-23rd day of the menstrual cycle using silver-containing IUDs or immediately after their removal.

Results. During the study it was revealed that the index of DNA accumulation in the glandular epithelium of the endometrium changed slightly. Only in the group of women who used IUDs for up to 1 year was the decrease in DNA content observed. In groups of women using silver-containing IUDs for a long time (more than 5–7 years), there is the tendency toward the decrease in the number of cells with intermediate DNA content and the increase with the tetraploid DNA set in the proliferative stage of the cycle ($P > 0.05$). Therefore, when using silver-containing IUDs in the glandular epithelium of the uterine mucosa, pathological proliferation of the endometrium is not observed, as well as when using indifferent plastic contraceptives.

Keywords: silver-containing intrauterine contraceptive devices, DNA, oncological risk, menstrual cycle.

Corresponding author:**Kupina A.D.,**

Clinical Resident

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education

«Rostov State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian

Federation, 344022, Russian Federation, Rostov region, Rostov-on-Don,

29 Nakhichevan lane.

Phone: 89518268150. E-mail: anastasya1997@bk.ru

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Hormonal and intrauterine contraceptives are the most commonly used means of preventing an unplanned pregnancy [1,2,3]. Many issues of intrauterine contraception are covered in the literature, but its oncological aspects have not been fully studied [4]. When using intrauterine contraceptives (IUDs), many researchers did not detect malignant growth [5,6,7,8], but revealed in some women various changes in the endometrium [9], including chronic non-specific endometritis [10,11,12], structural asynchronism endometrial transformations, focal and glandular hyperplasia [13,14] adenoacanthosis, polyposis, etc. [15]. According to K.P. Ganina [16] the causes of the development of malignant tumors can be: a long-existing inflammatory process that violates tissue trophism, unevenly proliferated lesions without a tendency to ripen, lesions and field of metaplasia arising from a chronic inflammatory process or hormonal imbalance.

Nowadays it has been established that malignant neoplasm cells are characterized by the higher DNA content in the nuclei, compared with normal tissue cells. In the process of carcinogenesis, along with the multiple increase in the DNA content in the nuclei of cells (ploidy), there is the increase in their heterogeneity in the DNA content [16,17,18,19].

The purpose of this study was to identify the proliferative properties of the endometrium, and therefore, to assess the risk of possible malignancy when using silver-containing IUDs by research of the DNA content in the epithelial cells of the glands of the uterine mucosa in women using this method of contraception.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The DNA content in the epithelial cells of the uterine mucosa glands was studied in 86 women of childbearing age with a normal menstrual cycle, having a history of one or more pregnancies and using silver-containing IUDs from 6 months to 7 years.

Endometrial biopsy with the microcurette or obtaining endometrial scrapings were performed on the 8-10th or 19-23rd day of the menstrual cycle using silver-containing IUDs or immediately after their removal.

For the study, preparations were selected in which the endometrium, against the background of the IUDs use, had no pathological changes and corresponded to the day of the menstrual cycle. The control group consisted of 15 women in whom the endometrial biopsy was performed before the introduction of silver-containing IUDs. DNA in

sections with a thickness of 6-7 microns was identified by Feilgen. The coloring conditions for all sections were the same. For quantitative determination of DNA, we used the method of adsorption cytophotometry on the integrating scanning microspectrophotometer. In each preparation, the amount of DNA was studied in 25-50 nuclei of epithelial cells and 25 nuclei of lymphocytes (the number of studied nuclei was determined by their spread in DNA content). For the amount of DNA corresponding to the diploid set of chromosomes (2n), the average DNA content in the nucleus of the lymphocyte of the same section was taken. The generalized kinetics of changes in the amount of DNA in the glandular epithelium of the endometrium (DNA accumulation index) was calculated, which is the average value of the sum of the products of the number of cells and the corresponding units of nuclear ploidy [16]. The results were compared with the control group, processed statistically using the Fisher LSD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In the control group, on the 8-10th day of the menstrual cycle, the index of DNA accumulation in the nuclei of the glandular epithelium cells of the endometrium was 2.8 ± 0.025 , the modal class were cells with a diploid set of DNA, the amount of which was 57.8%. The polyploidy of the epithelial cells was not large: cells with a hypertetraploid DNA content amounted to 3.7%, tetraploid nuclei there were 12.9%. The number of cells with an intermediate (3n) DNA content (25.6%) is rather high in the proliferating endometrium.

In the middle stage of secretion of control cycles, the index of DNA accumulation in the nuclei of glandular endometrium cells was 2.72 ± 0.03 , cells with diploid nuclei predominated (47.8%), the number of cells with the intermediate set of DNA increased (33.2%) . Compares with the proliferation stage, cells with the hypodiploid DNA content (3.9%) also appeared in the uterine mucosa, cells with tetraploid nuclei were found more often (15.1%, $P > 0.05$), and cells with the hypertetraploid content were not found.

Thus, the study showed that the index of DNA accumulation in the cells of the endometrial glands during the control menstrual cycle changed slightly. Data on the distribution of cells by ploidy in various phases of the control menstrual cycle indicate the predominance of cells with the diploid set of DNA. The presence of hypertetraploid cells in the proliferative phase and the appearance of cells with the hypoploid DNA content in the secretory phase of the menstrual cycle were also noted.

In the group of women who used silver-containing IUDs up to 1 year old, a statistically insignificant decrease in the index of DNA accumulation was noted. In the proliferation phase, this indicator decreased to 2.71 ± 0.015 , in the secretion phase to 2.59 ± 0.046 . On the 8-10th day of the menstrual cycle, the population was dominated by cells with diploid DNA content (60.8%), the number of cells with an intermediate set of DNA was 21.9%, with tetraploid - 12.5%. Cells appeared with a hypodiploid DNA content (2.2%). On the 19-23rd day of the cycle, in the epithelium of the endometrial glands, the modal class was cells in the G1 period (50.1%). The number of cells in the S period did not change compared to the control cycles and amounted to 33.2%, cells in the G2 period were detected only in 10.6%.

In the group of women who used IUDs for 1-3 years, the index of DNA accumulation in the nuclei of glandular cells slightly exceeded the data of the control group and was 2.79 ± 0.05 ($P > 0.05$) in the middle phase of proliferation and 2.68 ± 0.025 ($P > 0.05$) in the middle phase of secretion. The distribution of cells by DNA content was similar to that in the control group. In the proliferation phase, cells with diploid DNA were 58.3%, of which hypodiploid cells were 1.7%, the number of cells with intermediate DNA content was 25.2%, with tetraploid 11.9%, the hypertetraploid composition was 2.9% of the cells. In the phase of secretion, the cells in the diploid mode prevailed (48%), the intermediate composition of DNA was noted in 32.9% of the nuclei. In the phase of secretion, the cells in the diploid mode prevailed (48%), the intermediate composition of DNA was noted in 32.9% of the nuclei. The number of tetraploid nuclei increased slightly (16.2%) ($P > 0.05$), while the number of hypodiploid nuclei decreased (2.9%) compares with the control group.

In the group of patients who used silver-containing IUDs for 3-5 years, the DNA accumulation index in the glandular epithelium was 2.74 ± 0.035 , in the proliferative stage it was slightly higher than in the secretory (2.7 ± 0.02). In both phases of the menstrual cycle, cells with a diploid DNA content prevailed in the epithelium of the endometrial glands, the number of which on the 8-10th day of the cycle was 54.8%, on the 19-23rd day - 49.5%. Along with this, cells with the tetraploid DNA content were found in the glands (15.1% in the middle proliferative phase and 13.8% in the middle secretory phase), cells with the intermediate set of DNA were 24.2 and 33.1%, respectively. Hypodiploid nuclei were determined in 1.2% in the secretory and 3.4% in the proliferative stage of the menstrual cycle.

When using silver-containing IUDs for 5-7 years, the DNA accumulation index remained at the control group level and amounted to 2.81 ± 0.05 in the middle proliferative stage and 2.69 ± 0.052 in the middle stage of secretion. The distribution of nuclei by the amount of DNA in the proliferative phase was still dominated by cells of the diploid region (56.1%). Along with this, the percentage of cells with tetraploid DNA content increased in glands (22.3%), however, this increase was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). Intermediate DNA was detected in 16.8% of the cells, hypodiploid - in 2.4%. On the 19-23rd day of the cycle, most of the cells were diploid DNA, they were 48.9% in the population. Cells with the tetraploid DNA content amounted to 17.2%, with the intermediate - 31.3%, with the hypodiploid - 2.6%.

CONCLUSION:

1. Thus, when using silver-containing IUDs, the index of DNA accumulation in the glandular epithelium of the endometrium changed slightly. Only in the group of women who used IUDs for up to 1 year was the decrease in DNA content observed. This may be a manifestation of the body's adaptation to intrauterine contraceptives and may be due to the violation of the utilization of steroid hormones in the cells of target organs [18]. However, the decrease in the proliferative activity of the endometrium was transient, and with the longer use of IUD, the normal DNA content was determined.
2. In groups of women using silver-containing IUDs for a long time (more than 5-7 years), there is the tendency toward the decrease in the number of cells with intermediate DNA content and the increase with the tetraploid DNA set in the proliferative stage of the cycle ($P > 0.05$). Regardless of the duration of the use of IUDs, the insignificant number of cells with the hypodiploid DNA content was determined in the middle stage of proliferation, which is apparently due to the destruction of part of the endometrial cells under the influence of the foreign body (intrauterine contraceptive).

Therefore, when using silver-containing IUDs in the glandular epithelium of the uterine mucosa, pathological proliferation of the endometrium is not observed, as well as when using indifferent plastic contraceptives.

List of symbols and Abbreviations

IUDs - intrauterine contraceptive devices

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